

Synthetic dataset generation for edge drone inference and training

Bogdan Nedelcu
Faculty of Automatic Control and Computers,
Politehnica University of Bucharest
bogdan.nedelcu@gmail.com

Adina Magda Florea
Faculty of Automatic Control and Computers,
Politehnica University of Bucharest
adina.florea@upb.ro

Abstract—This research investigates the generation of synthetic aerial images for training deep neural networks, particularly targeting the task of object detection in mostly top-down views. The experiment leveraged a simulation environment to create a complex dataset, addressing the challenges associated with collecting real-world aerial images. The work encompassed several critical components, including algorithm parameter variation for ground truth annotation, the exploration of bounding box generation techniques and an investigation into camera orientations and altitude to simulate real-world scenarios. Additionally, the research delved into the training of neural network models, specifically tailored for low-power devices, particularly the Coral Edge TPU. The findings of this research indicate the feasibility of utilizing synthetic environments and datasets to train neural networks for aerial image analysis. The trained model showcased promising results, with the potential for broader applications in object detection. The study also addressed safety considerations, emphasizing the need for high-resolution cameras in drone operations to detect objects, such as human bodies, from safe distances. Furthermore, the paper outlines a roadmap for future work, highlighting areas such as multi-class object detection, integration with autopilot systems, and real-world testing. This research serves as a foundational step toward harnessing synthetic data and deep learning for enhanced drone capabilities in diverse scenarios, with a commitment to safety and compliance with aviation regulations.

Keywords — *edge-tpu, drone, unmanned systems regulations, simulated environments, synthetic dataset.*

I. INTRODUCTION

European regulations on drone operations are well established from 2019 and updated continuously to facilitate both the adoption of such technology in the industry and to the safety of the operations. Starting January 2024 [1] a new classification and updated regulations were enforced on drones flying in the open category, where many low-risk drone activities are performed.

One notable change is the introduction of a remote identification requirement, applicable to all drones in the open category. This additional mandate underscores the growing necessity to enhance drones with new technology, marking a significant step toward their safety and integration in civil activities. However, existing regulations still enforce line-of-sight drone operations, meaning that either the pilot or an assistant must maintain visual contact with the drone and intervene in case of emergency.

Synthetic image generation for training deep neural networks (DNN) has become a pivotal approach in the field of aerial imagery analysis, especially for object detection tasks viewed from top-down perspectives. This approach is driven by the need for vast, diverse datasets, which are often costly or impractical to gather through real-world means. Synthetic imagery offers a

controllable, scalable alternative, enabling the simulation of various environmental conditions and object interactions that are essential for developing robust detection models. By generating synthetic images with corresponding ground truth annotations, we can produce large volumes of diverse labeled data sets for training purposes given the fact that aerial images are difficult to gather in the context of weather conditions, camera orientation, visibility. Training a DNN which could fit inside an edge computer and running entirely inside the drone is a big step towards drone autonomy.

The main aim of this paper is to explore dataset creation, for DNN training towards autonomously flying drones in simulated environment and real world. Our objective is to create an end-to-end pipeline from dataset generation to training and running models on specific edge devices in order to be able to address real-world tasks which might not be particularly suited with generalized datasets and existing architectures of existing DNNs. The paper is organized as follows. Section II briefly presents related work. Section III describes the experiment with a drone in real-world and takes note how the earth appears from above using a small on-board camera attached to the drone. We take note of the size of the objects and identify some rules to use when gathering images from online sources such as Google Earth. Section IV explores the use of 3D simulation environment for generating training data for neural networks initially for house detection and later use the same procedure for other types of objects such as humans, cars, buses, vans, etc. Our objective is to leverage the capabilities of a 3D simulation environment to create a broad dataset matching real-world scenarios for which otherwise would be difficult to obtain such information. We focus on house detection as the simplest environment available in the simulation environment and continue to explore augmenting the dataset with several factors to improve the diversity.

Section V consider integrating a drone with deep learning capabilities, one by using a companion computer with an embedded efficient Coral Edge TPU [2] processor operating in real world and another one as a HIL (hardware in the loop) operating inside a simulation environment using the same Edge TPU. We detail all the setup needed to configure both system architectures and then run inside the simulation environment an object detection DNN fine-tuned on VisDrone [3] dataset.

II. RELATED WORK

Generating synthetic data, especially for complex applications like object detection from aerial perspectives, may be approached with different methodologies, such as simulation and rendering engines, generative adversarial networks, data augmentation techniques or physics-based simulation.

Simulation environments can be used to generate synthetic training data, where both high fidelity and the ability to create diverse scenarios automatically are key features [4]. A wide range of simulation environments exists, from Gazebo2, which is used for controller development, to the photorealistic flight simulator X-Plane3 for pilot training. Positioned between these is AirSim [5], a simulation tool for autonomous vehicles that utilizes the Unreal Engine4. This engine's marketplace offers access to various environments and human models. AirSim has also been utilized for deep learning-based pedestrian classification [6]. However, none of these tools are primarily designed for creating synthetic training data.

Other tools like VERIFAI [7] serve to bridge simulation with machine learning training and verification. VERIFAI, for instance, uses existing simulators to verify deep neural networks for perception tasks and incorporates SCENIC [Fr], a language for automatic scene generation. Presently, these tools do not support in-air scenarios.

III. REAL WORLD IMAGE ANALYSIS FROM DRONE

A. Experimental setup

The objective of this experiment is to determine the size and appearance of objects as viewed from a small camera embedded on a drone, camera which is suited to work with a neural network inside the drone to process images live and give feedback to the drone's auto pilot. This experiment is needed to validate the size of the objects in simulator to obtain images as close as possible to reality. For this experiment we used a custom-built drone of 1.7kg based on a HGDRONEK66 [8] NXP drone kit.

The drone was linked to a ground control station through telemetry radio, allowing us to monitor the parameters of the drone in real time. Below the drone we mounted the Coral Mini Board with Camera attached, pointing downwards, and connected to a separate battery supplying USB (universal serial bus) standard voltage. The camera mounted on the drone is Omni Vision OV5645 SoC, Auto focus, focal length 2.5mm, range 10cm-infinity, 84.0 degrees / 87.6 degrees, 5-megapixel.

Fig. 1. Images taken at 10, 30 and 80m height. To determine the size of the images viewed at different heights above the ground we performed the following experiment. We fly the camera at different heights, maintain altitude and gather images of the ground.

To validate our experiment and for future reference we take the same images from the neighborhood in the Google Earth software. Notice the camera height reported by Google Earth is 271m above sea level, leading to approx. 190m above ground, compared to our image of the same surface of the ground which is taken at 100m. This is mostly related to different camera FOV (Field of View); however, this is important to note in order be able to use images from Google Earth in potential future simulations.

By comparing images captured from the drone to images from Google Earth (Fig. 1) we try to identify the table of correspondence at different heights and note the similarity in images.

TABLE 1: TABLE OF CORRESPONDENCE BETWEEN DRONE CAMERA HEIGHT AND GOOGLE EARTH CAMERA.

Distance above ground from drone in meters	Camera height from ground in Google Earth in meters	Observations regarding visual similarity
20	47	Images distorted
30	72	Images differ slightly
40	87	Images visually similar
50	97	Images visually similar
60	118	Images visually similar
70	132	Images visually similar
80	157	Images visually similar
90	175	Images visually similar
100	185	Images visually similar

We note a linear correspondence between the two variables which may be depicted in the following image.

Fig. 2: Measured relationship between height of the drone camera (above ground) and Google Earth camera distance in Bucharest

Note: To get a visual similar image of the earth at a H distance from ground with the Google Coral Camera 5MP we may use Google Earth and get images from the following height

$$\text{Height of photo camera} = H \times 1.7 + 152$$

We note this rule as it will be used further on as a formula when capturing data for creating the future train/test/validate dataset in synthetic environments.

B. Considerations on the resolution of the image

To measure the characteristics of the acquired images we align all images to a resolution of 640x480 pixels and measure the size of the pixels in centimeters taking into consideration the measured information visible in all images. The red roof present in the image measures 1150 centimeters and the width of a car present in the image is 1700 centimeters. For future reference

we also compute the width in pixels of a human body, using an average shoulder width of 48 cm and body depth of 36 cm.

Fig. 3: Calibration of pixel size on the Google Coral Camera

We verify the calculus using visual zoomed image of a car in the following two pictures and observe correct results in number of pixels for the width of the object at 100m and 50m distance from the object.

Fig.4: Zoomed in image used for calibration where at 100m altitude the width of a car is between 8-10 pixels

C. Considerations on the EASA regulations for human avoidance

Guidelines by EASA (European Aviation Safety Agency) for drone operations stipulate that C2 Type of drones must follow some regulations when flying in the vicinity of people. Since our plan is to improve this class of drones with human detection capabilities, we shall consider these limitations when creating a training dataset. Therefore, we must be able to detect at 30-40 meters the human body, hence the camera resolution and the processing power of the neural network onboard the drone must be able to handle this type of information.

Fig.5: Relationship between height of the drone camera and the observed human body size

A raw formula for the linear dependence of height of drone to human body width in pixels at 640x480 resolution is:

$$\text{Height of drone} = -18.7 * \text{Pixels} + 123.47$$

Given the above graph we analyze visually shapes of the human body in correspondence with the size in pixels, identifying the height a drone should fly to obtain those images for a sensor size of 640x480.

Fig. 6: Several images of the same body size at various resolutions (source: <http://dronedataset.icg.tugraz.at/>)

In Fig. 6 we measure 4 sizes: 4, 6, 9 and 13 pixels width of the human body in each of the 4 different scales of the image.

Given the proposed sensor of 640x480 we conclude that a clear visible shape of the human body is at above 6 pixels width between shoulders. Taking into consideration that EASA ruling proposing a safe distance of 30 meters and considering a buffer of 10-20 meters before reaching this safe distance we need to be able to detect the human body from approximately 50 meters straight distance.

TABLE 2: HUMAN BODY SHOULDERS WIDTH AT DIFFERENT CAMERA RESOLUTIONS

Human body shoulders width in pixels at 50 meters	Camera resolution (at approx. 90 deg FOV)	Camera resolution class
3.70	640x480	Reference value
2.08	360x240	CIF
4.16	720x576	D1
5.55	960x576	960H
7.40	1280x720	HD
11.10	1920x1080	Full HD
14.99	2592x1520	4MP
14.99	2592x1920	5MP

Note: analyzing the camera resolutions in Table 2 we conclude a safe choice for human body visibility at 90 degrees FOV, at 50m altitude are cameras with a resolution above HD (1280 x 720)

This is an important remark because this type of resolution influences the size of the input of the neural network thus influencing the parameters of the neural network in order to process a larger number of pixels in order to detect these types of objects.

IV. SYNTHETIC DATASET GENERATION

A. Basic technique and environment

Our overall objective was to experiment with generating a dataset containing images and annotations as bounding boxes from aerial photos to be used in training of a neural network to detect objects.

We used the AirSim plugin of Unreal with the environment named AirSimNH - a 3D neighborhood with houses and perpendicular roads surrounded by trees which we introduced later as a training dataset for an object detection network. To generate the ground truth we performed some preprocessing of the information we receive from the simulator.

The problem we faced was that for any rendered scene in the 3D engine we must be able to get the list of visible surfaces from a camera field of view. We must filter and join areas of the surfaces to get a reasonable list of bounding boxes overlapped over the generated image. The surfaces in the 3D environment are 3D objects of different type which are named by the author of the 3D landscape when building the environment.

For each of these surfaces we can obtain the bounding boxes using the Python function *simGetDetections* to return the list of boxes relative to the pixels of the images captured by that specific camera (Fig. 7).

For any camera taking pictures in this simulated environment, we need to set the FOV of the camera prior to capturing an image using the following functions:

- `simSetVehiclePose`
- `simSetCameraFov` (we used camera “0” with FOV 0.87)

Fig.7: Bounding boxes of all objects visible as rendered by the 3D engine at 50m height, with a yaw of 80 degrees (90 degrees orthogonal to ground)

As our objective is to identify the bounding boxes of the houses automatically such that we can feed this info to a DNN training pipeline, we choose a subset of the surface names which are the most representative for the houses given a view from above: "Roof", "Porch", "Veranda", "Outer_Wall", "Small_House", "Medium_House". These elements correspond only to items which compose a house in this environment. We observe that some buildings are made of several surfaces and expose several bounding boxes which overlap to some degree. Therefore, we choose an IoU (Intersection over Union) metric in order to join the bounding boxes of each individual building.

Fig. 8 Bounding boxes filtered for "Roof", "Porch", "Veranda", "Outer_Wall"

Fig. 9 Bounding boxes filtered and merged using IoU threshold of 0.1

One can observe that small objects are not handled well together with large objects because the IoU is very small compared to the union, due to the small area of the small objects. We will address this issue using another filter which considers the Intersection over Minimum, in order to be able to merge small objects into larger ones.

$$IoM_{xy}(D_i, G_i) = \frac{\text{Area of } D_i \cap G_i}{\min\{\text{Area of } D_i, \text{Area of } G_i\}} \in [0, 1], \quad [9]$$

Fig. 10 Bounding boxes merged using IoM threshold of 0.3

We observe in Fig. 10 that the IoM function performs better than the IoU, for our given task to join the small and large surfaces into a single object. We note that in the coordinates of the picture if we keep all houses edges to be parallel with image edges the algorithm has difficulty merging bounding boxes as they do not overlap at all.

Limitations: we observe in Fig. 10 the algorithm is not giving perfect results due to the nature of the detected boxes not being rotated along with the shape of the objects they bound and therefore the area of intersecting boxes does not reflect the real object proximity.

For the given altitude and the specific objects present in this simulation environment we determine empirically that a value of 0.3 is best suited for the IoM threshold to decide if we merge two bounding boxes or not. For other environments, this value needs to be determined empirically as each environment is composed of different textures and objects.

B. Variations techniques for environment augmentation

Capturing images during flight will be influenced by external and internal factors of our system therefore we must be able to get synthetic data like real world inclination of the camera. Drones position during flight is influenced by external factors such as wind or rain and by internal factors such as direction and speed. When a quadcopter drone moves forward relative to ground it will lower its forward two motors and heighten the back motors in order for the propellers to generate thrust partially from back to front, moving the drone forward [10].

To address variability of the generated dataset we factor in several degrees of freedom for the camera. We assume drones camera FOV is oriented downwards to the center of the earth, meaning they will see the ground surface as flat, undistorted by inclination. Commercial drones have the maximum pitch angle set between 30 and 45 degrees depending on the speed needed or wind condition. Given this value range we must assume collecting images with FOV oriented between -45 and 45 degrees.

TABLE 3: ALGORITHM PARAMETERS USED TO GENERATE A DIVERSE SET OF IMAGES OF THE GROUND.

Param	Min (degrees)	Max (degrees)	Set of values (radians)
Pitch	45	90	[0.78, 1.17, 1.57]
Roll	0	45	[0.01, 0.39, 0.78]
Yaw	0	45	[0.1, 0.39, 0.78]

To simulate these types of orientations of the drone we change the parameters of the orientation of the camera to the range of values presented in Table 3. At vertical Pitch we observe the Roll and Yaw generate the same rotation of the camera therefore producing the same type of image (Fig. 11). To have a good distribution of images we choose to ignore Yaw changes at Pitch 90° therefore leaving us with a total of 21 images.

Fig. 11: Variations of the orientations and the respective bounding boxes located in the camera image

Furthermore to improve the variability of the dataset we use 8 weather parameters to change in order to simulate different

weather conditions: Rain, Roadwetness, Snow, RoadSnow, MapleLeaf, RoadLeaf, Dust, Fog.

TABLE 4: TABLE OF WEATHER CONDITIONS PARAMETERS

Parameter	Min	Max
Fog	0%	20%
Dust	0%	50%
RoadLeaf	0%	50%
RoadSnow	0%	20%

The weather conditions give us a multiplier of the total number of possible images of 4, therefore we have $21 \times 4 = 84$ generated images.

Altitude is another parameter which we may vary for the done, it is the altitude relative to the ground, in our case the ground of the simulated environment is 0 meters.

TABLE 5: ALTITUDE PARAMETERS VARIATIONS AS ALTITUDES IDENTIFIED PREVIOUSLY IN SECTION 3

Altitude (meters)	Point 1	Point 2	Point 3	Point 4
	40m	70m	100m	130m

The altitude parameter (Table 5) introduces a multiplication factor of 4 to the existing number of images taken from one point. Total number of images generated for one point in the 2D map is given by the formula:

$$\text{Weather} \times \text{Altitude} \times \text{Orientation} = 4 \times 4 \times 21 = 336 \text{ images}$$

To identify the total number of points one must divide the 2D space into several matrices depending on the height, more detailed on low altitude and less detailed on higher altitude.

The purpose of this image generation process is to retrain a DNN model compatible with a low power device such as the Google Coral micro board. We save each image in JPG format and annotations in XML format according to Pascal VOC convention.

For testing purposes, we use the YOLOV5 network architecture version Small which is best optimized to run on embedded devices as it features a small number of parameters. We start with a pre-trained COCO model of YOLOv5, and a small dataset of 7560 generated images of 3 levels of altitude and several orientations to test the model performance, split in 3 sets as follows: 5292 for training, 1512 for validation and 756 for testing. The generated dataset contained images with a balanced number of variations of the orientation of the camera towards earth, gathering both small, medium and large objects from different angles.

The figure bellow shows an overview of where the annotations are present in images of the datasets, showing a good balance in the 2D space, not clustering near any specific part of the image.

Training on the set of 5292 images (samples below) converges smoothly after 400 iterations, the tiny model being able to achieve a MAP50 of 0.75 on the validation set.

We proceed to compile the model on a mobile device and test it against live images in AirSIM using the camera of the mobile phone and the AirSIM in full screen mode, at a distance of 20 cm. We observe promising results, all houses in the image are detected with a bounding box positioned accordingly.

Fig. 12: Live test on the 3D images of the trained model on a mobile phone 12, running at 24 FPS on the live image stream on a monitor presenting the camera view. In the images below we note the FPS of the model along with the time it took to process the captured frame

This experiment made it possible to verify end-to-end that a pipeline with synthetic environment generated images is possible to train a tiny object detector and use it real-time on a device.

C. Introducing human assets in simulation environments

There is a broad range of environments to choose from in the Unreal Marketplace which may be customized. To continue our experiment, we used the City Park Environment as one which offers both vegetation and roads, but there are many others available [11].

To simulate human characters and cars we investigated two character repositories: the MetaHuman and Actor Core. MetaHuman provides high quality facial expressions and high-fidelity details of the human body while ActorCore provides custom built human characters with complex set of animations which you can mix. Since our interactions with the scene are in general at a fair distance, more than 10 meters, our interest is to see in the scene as many human positions as possible while not in such detail as MetaHuman would provide. We chose ActorCore as our source of actors since the animations provided gives us more entropy in the system.

The ActorCore Character represents a special 3D character category featuring photorealistic individuals generated through 3D scanning. It is easy to incorporate these animation-ready characters using application-specific download formats to achieve optimal rendering quality in 3D engines such as Unreal. The adjustable material functionality allows for the limitless customization of appearance, combining various colors and material styles for ActorCore characters.

The AirSim simulator has the capability to integrate these characters and animate them through standard Unreal functionalities with options for customizing character appearance, including fabric colors, animations, and postures.

After following customizations of the Unreal Environment and experimenting with basic animations we were able to introduce

in a test environment and later in the CityPark environment some human characters and other assets such as humans, cars, vans and buses.

Fig.13: Testing the character animations in a Unreal Engine environment

V. INTEGRATING EDGE COMPUTER WITH DRONE HARDWARE

A. General Approach

Integrating the equipment inside the drone must consider the available connections and protocol of the autopilot, namely the PX4 hardware. We choose the PX4 autopilot as one of the two possible options for open-source pilots: Ardupilot and PX4 [12]. The companion computer will connect to quadcopter drone PX4 autopilot through a serial port used to send commands and receive telemetry data stream.

The custom developed software is used to pre-process the images from the camera, send them to the neural network and process the results in order to send custom commands to the drone. The quadcopter drone PX4 autopilot receives commands from the companion computer but also from 2 other sources such as the Remote Radio Control and the Ground Control station software which is used for mission planning and high level monitoring.

Fig. 14. A high-level communication diagram between the above mentioned components during typical autonomous mission.

The initiation of the mission is started by the companion computer, commands are sent through the communication link to the autopilot which can also be monitored by the Ground Control console.

This architecture is designed to satisfy safety requirements and mitigate risks during mission execution, as stated in EASA Regulations [13]. The drone will always execute missions in line of sight under direct supervision of the drone pilot which will monitor the parameters of the drone on the Ground Control console and command the drone using the Radio Remote control.

B. Hardware integration

The communication links and protocols of the real-life hardware are mostly serial links implemented over radio or wired between components. The diagram in Fig 16. depicts the conceptual integration between each component. This drone model is a popular choice as it is fairly extensible and falls under the 2kg MTOW (Maximum TakeOff Weight) category C2/A2 stipulated by the EASA Regulations starting January 1st 2024.

Fig. 16: Integration architecture of the drone with the companion computer presenting the schema of the PX4 interconnection with the Flight Controller as recommended in the architecture of the PX4 autopilot documentation.

Fig. 15: Connection between companion computer and PX4 auto pilot using 3 wire UART serial connection.

One must note that all the serial communication channels use the MAVLink protocol, a protocol built on purpose to command-and-control drones which is implemented by a large majority of autopilots available on the market at this point in time. Our companion computer uses a subset of the MAVLink protocol to monitor the parameters of the drone and to give new commands.

PX4 flight computer has a dedicated serial port called TELEM2 on which we can activate the MAVLink protocol to exchange messages with a companion computer, in our case the Google Coral Mini board. We will use serial UART (universal asynchronous receiver / transmitter) pins of the coral mini number 29, 31 and 36 as ground. These pins are allocated to serial device under the Linux operating system named /dev/ttyS1 as visible in Fig. 17. On the PX4 board we will connect the wires (3.3v) using a dedicated connector. To test the communication with PX4 autopilot was performed by changing the address of the drone to: `serial:///dev/ttyS1`

C. Integrating simulator with HIL

HIL, or Hardware In the Loop is often used to test electronic equipment in real life scenarios supplied by simulators. In our case we decided to create a simulator environment and put all our electronic equipment (Autopilot and Companion Computer) to run in this simulated world and test the behavior. This integration is mainly for performing experiments of the command and control of the drone and not to gather images for training data.

The simulator is designed to simulate real-world sensors and actuators to the electronics in the following way:

- AirSim integrates PX4 in HIL mode, allowing a complete immersive experience of flying a quadcopter drone inside the simulator.
- AirSim exposes API to gather images from virtual cameras inside the simulator to extract close to real-life imagery from onboard sensors.

Once the environment is setup we may integrate the AirSim plugin inside this Unreal environment in order to add the drone and execute basic navigations. The following image shows the connected components which composes the HIL electronics used to integrate in the simulated environment.

Fig. 17: The HIL components: 1. The PX4 Autopilot, 2. The Google Coral Edge TPU Accelerator USB module, 3. The Radio Remote Control, 4. The Serial2USB adaptor, 5. The telemetry radio

One important observation is that this simulated environment for the PX4 autopilot is functional similar to real-life, as the autopilot receives sensor information and sends commands through the same interfaces, even flight monitoring through Ground Control Station is in place.

D. Testing fine tuned DNN in simulation environment

Starting from a pretrained model of YOLOv5n6u we fine-tuned it on the VisDrone dataset in order to have capability to recognize humans/cars from above and deploy it inside the Coral Edge TPU. We choose YOLOv5 since the v8 version has an architecture which does not fit in the Edge TPU entirely and because of the flexibility to extend this architecture with several prediction heads for small object detection [10].

The data split of the training set is the following: 75% train, 6.5 validation, 18.5 testing. The detection classes are: pedestrian, people, bicycle, car, van, truck, tricycle, awning-tricycle, bus, motor. We present in Annex the metrics of the training process for 100 epochs, at image size 640x640 with a batch size of 32. We exported the model with a preset image size of 256x256 as this was the biggest value the model fits completely in the Coral

Edge TPU. The Fig. 18 we show depicts how the model looks as compiled for the edge-tpu.

Fig.18: Compiled model on the Edge TPU: on the left not fitting entirely on the processor memory and on the right fitting entirely.

We observe that a fully deployable to EdgeTPU model must be compiled as one single operation, input size is a quantized integer matrix of $[256,256,3]$ while the output is a tensor of $[1,14,1360]$ with the yolo classes and bounding boxes. In particular for this model the quantization parameters are $0.010388271883130074 * (q + 128)$.

We present below some of the images captured while “flying” in the simulation environment.

Fig. 19: Captured images of the drone and detected objects in live camera images inside the simulated environment

We observe that the model detects with good precision the bounding boxes, detects classes and runs in real time on the Edge TPU processor entirely.

VI. CONCLUSIONS AND FUTURE WORK

In this paper, we addressed the challenges associated with the labor-intensive and time-consuming process of creating annotated datasets for training neural networks, specifically for object detection in top-down views from aerial images. We explored the potential of synthetic data generation using a 3D simulation environment, focusing on the application to drone autonomy and compliance with evolving drone regulations.

The experiment involved real-world drone flights to analyze the size and appearance of objects from different altitudes. We established a rule for capturing images from Google Earth based on drone height, facilitating the creation of a future synthetic dataset. Considerations on image resolution were made, taking into account the requirements for human body detection as stipulated by EASA regulations.

The main focus shifted to synthetic dataset generation using the AirSim Unreal plugin, with a specific emphasis on house detection. We overcame challenges in bounding box generation by introducing Intersection over Minimum (IoM) to merge small objects, enhancing the dataset's diversity. Weather conditions and altitude variations were also considered to simulate real-world scenarios, and a YOLOv5 network architecture was fine-tuned on this synthetic dataset.

The integration of human assets in simulation environments using human characters marked a significant step toward enhancing the realism of the generated datasets. We demonstrated the integration of edge computing with drone hardware, detailing the communication protocols and connections required for real-time processing of images.

Furthermore, we conducted Hardware in the Loop (HIL) testing to validate the behavior of electronic components in a simulated environment. The testing involved fine-tuning a YOLOv5n6u model on the VisDrone dataset and deploying it on the Coral Edge TPU, showcasing promising results in object detection during simulated drone flights.

This research represents a step forward towards leveraging synthetic data for enhanced drone capabilities. The study aligns with the evolving drone regulations, emphasizing safety, compliance, and the potential for future advancements in multi-class object detection, integration with autopilot systems, and real-world testing. The findings contribute to the broader goal of harnessing synthetic data for training neural networks in drone applications, advancing for safer and more efficient drone operations in diverse scenarios.

Future work will be focused on generating an extended dataset derived from multiple high-fidelity simulation environments. These simulations will include a variety of dynamic elements such as moving people, cars, and other assets. This synthetic dataset aims to simulate real-world conditions more accurately, thereby providing a robust foundation for further research and development contributing to our main goal of enabling drones with higher degree of autonomy.

Building upon these synthetic datasets, the next phase will involve improving the detection of various objects. This will be achieved by employing finely tuned detection models specifically trained using the newly created dataset targeting the low power processors. The objective will be to enhance the accuracy and reliability of object detection under diverse and realistic scenarios simulated within the dataset.

Another direction will involve the introduction of advanced planning policies for the flying drone. These policies will include mechanisms for self-adaptation during flight operations. The aim is to enable autonomous systems to dynamically adjust their strategies in response to real-time changes and challenges, thus meeting predefined objectives more effectively.

ACKNOWLEDGMENT

This work was supported by the European Union’s Horizon Europe research and innovation program under the grant agreement No. 101120657, project ENFIELD (European Lighthouse to Manifest Trustworthy and Green AI).

REFERENCES

- [1] "Open Category - Low Risk - Civil Drones", 2024, European Union Aviation Safety Agency [Online]. Available: <https://www.easa.europa.eu/en/domains/civil-drones-rpas/open-category-civil-drones>
- [2] Seyedehfaezeh Hosseininoorbin, Siamak Layeghy, Brano Kusy, Raja Jurdak, Marius Portmann, "Exploring Deep Neural Networks on Edge TPU" 2021, arXiv:2110.08826v2. [Online]. Available: <https://arxiv.org/abs/2110.08826>
- [3] Pengfei Zhu, Longyin Wen, Xiao Bian, Haibin Ling, Qinghua Hu, "Vision Meets Drones: A Challenge" 2018, arXiv:1804.07437v2. [Online]. Available: <https://doi.org/10.48550/arXiv.1804.07437>
- [4] Nikolaus Mayer, Eddy Ilg, Philipp Fischer, Caner Hazirbas, Daniel Cremers, Alexey Dosovitskiy, Thomas Brox, "What Makes Good Synthetic Training Data for Learning Disparity and Optical Flow Estimation?" International Journal of Computer Vision 126, 942–960 (2018). DOI: 10.1007/s11263-018-1082-6
- [5] Shital Shah, Debadepta Dey, Chris Lovett, Ashish Kapoor, "AirSim: High-Fidelity Visual and Physical Simulation for Autonomous Vehicles" 2017, arXiv:1705.05065v2. [Online]. Available: <https://doi.org/10.48550/arXiv.1705.05065>
- [6] Schleusner, J.; Neu, L.; Behmann, N.; Blume, H. "Deep Learning Based Classification of Pedestrian Vulnerability Trained on Synthetic Datasets" 2019 IEEE 9th International Conference on Consumer Electronics (ICCEBerlin). Berlin, Germany, 8. Sep. 2019. Available: DOI:10.1109/ICCE-Berlin47944.2019.8966161
- [7] Tommaso Dreossi, Daniel J. Fremont, Shromona Ghosh, Edward Kim, Hadi Ravanbakhsh, Marcell Vazquez-Chanlatte, Sanjit A. Seshia, "VerifAI: A Toolkit for the Formal Design and Analysis of Artificial Intelligence-Based Systems" 2019, arXiv:1902.04245v2. [Online]. Available: <https://doi.org/10.48550/arXiv.1902.04245>
- [8] "NXP Drone kit including RDDRONE-FMUK66 and peripherals" NXP Semiconductors, 2024. [Online]. Available: <https://www.nxp.com/design/design-center/designs/nxp-hovergames-drone-kit-including-rddrone-fmuk66-and-peripherals:KIT-HGDRONEK66>
- [9] Fabian W. Vogel, Sercan Alipek, Jens-Bastian Eppler, Pamela Osuna-Vargas, Jochen Triesch, Diane Bissen, Amparo Acker-Palmer, Simon Rumpel & Matthias Kaschube, "Utilizing 2D-region-based CNNs for automatic dendritic spine detection in 3D live cell imaging". Sci Rep 13, 20497 (2023). DOI:10.1038/s41598-023-47070-
- [10] Xingkui Zhu, Shuchang Lyu, Xu Wang, Qi Zhao, "TPH-YOLOv5: Improved YOLOv5 Based on Transformer Prediction Head for Object Detection on Drone-captured Scenarios," 2021 IEEE/CVF International Conference on Computer Vision Workshops (ICCVW), Montreal, BC, Canada, 2021, pp. 2778-2788. DOI: 10.1109/ICCVW54120.2021.00312
- [11] "Unreal Engine Environments" 2024, Epic Games repository. [Online]. Available: <https://www.unrealengine.com/marketplace/en-US/content-cat/assets/environments>
- [12] Bogdan Nedelcu and Adina Magda Florea, "Analysis of design solutions for autonomous drones," 2023 24th International Conference on Control Systems and Computer Science (CSCS), Bucharest, Romania, 2023, pp. 92-98, DOI: 10.1109/CSCS59211.2023.00024
- [13] "Easy Access Rules for Unmanned Aircraft Systems (Regulations (EU) 2019/947 and 2019/945)" 2024, European Union Aviation Safety Agency [Online]. Available: <https://www.easa.europa.eu/en/document-library/easy-access-rules/easy-access-rules-unmanned-aircraft-systems-regulations-eu>